

Experiment Design for Data Science

Exercise 2: PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference - Group 32

Ardit Luzi
TU Wien
Vienna, Austria
e12226089@student.tuwien.ac.at

Kaltrina Beha
TU Wien
Vienna, Austria
e12143763@student.tuwien.ac.at

Ora Hashani
TU Wien
Vienna, Austria
e12140188@student.tuwien.ac.at

Don Krasniqi
TU Wien
Vienna, Austria
e12140189@student.tuwien.ac.at

ABSTRACT

The publication references the code used to repeat the experiment, however, the final version has merge issues. Despite being available, it's challenging to reproduce the results because of poor documentation. Additionally, the packages in the given repository are outdated. We attempted to repeat the experiment using both versions of the code, but we faced difficulties as the packages could not be downgraded to resolve the errors we encountered. A further explanation of the results will be provided.

KEYWORDS

Recommendation systems, BERT, reproducibility, emoji recommendation, deep learning

1 INTRODUCTION

Emoji is a unique form of symbolic communication that conveys diverse emotions. It is widely used on social media, with around 90% of users regularly incorporating them into tweets, resulting in the daily transmission of 6 billion emojis. Emojis are graphical representations of human facial expressions and body language that add vibrancy to short tweets by allowing users to express their feelings more vividly. The number of emojis has greatly increased in recent years, with 1144 defined in Unicode 10.0 and 112 added in Unicode 14.0. With such a large number of options, users may find it challenging to quickly choose an emoji from the many available on social media platforms.

This has led to the development of the emoji prediction task, which aims to predict the emojis that are likely to accompany plain text. As a result, it has become a crucial task in recommendation systems.

Several matrix factorization-based methods[4] and deep learning-based methods[1][2][3] have been proposed for the emoji prediction task. However, these methods either don't take into account user preferences in emoji selection or only learn fixed user preferences for different tweet texts. Moreover, historical tweets of users are neglected, which could be valuable for modeling user preferences and providing personalized and diverse emoji recommendations. To overcome these limitations, we present the Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference (PERD) model. The core of our model is a text encoder and personalized attention mechanism. The text encoder utilizes a pre-trained BERT model to learn tweet text representations. To address the fact that historical tweets with varying semantics and sentiments reflect different aspects of user preference, the personalized attention mechanism is designed to identify relevant historical tweets and dynamically generate user preferences.

- The development of a Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference (PERD) model that leverages plain text and user historical tweets to provide personalized emoji recommendations. Experiments have shown that our model outperforms baseline models.

Reproducibility: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference

- The creation of a personalized attention module that dynamically generates user preference representations by learning from text and emojis in historical tweets. The personalized attention module identifies informative historical tweets and weights the emoji labels in those tweets to produce dynamic preferences. Below we can see the figure of the architecture of our PERD model for emoji recommendation.

However, there is a bright side to this repository. The datasets provided are well organized and the documentation is clear, indicating which data was used in the research. This makes it easier to understand the results and build upon the research. The repository includes two

2 REPRODUCIBILITY

The code for the research paper was made available to the public through the authors' Github repository. The code is split into multiple files, making it easier to manage, but also making it more complex to understand and utilize. The repository contains two main components: the BERT implementation, which is based on a Google NLP model, and the PRED implementation, which is responsible for encoding the emojis and processing the data.

Unfortunately, the code is poorly maintained and there are multiple instances of methods with similar functionality and inconsistent naming conventions. This, combined with errors leftover from previous commits, makes it difficult to understand the code and reproduce the results. For example, the commit number was included in every file, making it necessary to go through each file and remove it before testing the code.

datasets: Weibo and Twitter, both of which can be used for further research in the field.

In conclusion, while the code in the Github repository is challenging to work with due to its poor maintenance and confusing structure, the datasets provided are well organized and provide valuable information for future research.

3 RESULTS

Our goal was to follow the steps outlined in the paper to reproduce its results on each dataset. To begin, we cloned the necessary repositories onto our machines and encountered challenges such as outdated packages and errors related to Tensorflow 1.15, an older version of the library used in the code. The implementation of the main

methods relied on this outdated version, leading to difficulties such as the discontinuation of the Flag method in Tensorflow versions higher than 1.15.

To tackle the issue we were facing with the outdated Tensorflow version, we first attempted to downgrade the Tensorflow version from the latest one. We thought that this could potentially solve the compatibility issues with other libraries used in the repository. However, after downgrading, the author did not provide us with an environment file, which resulted in further difficulties with the compatibility of the other libraries. This process of trying to figure out the right versions for all the libraries was time-consuming and required a lot of trial and error.

Another approach we took was to try and write the code independently of any libraries, in an effort to make it library agnostic. The idea behind this was to provide the same functionality as the repository code but without relying on any of the old libraries. This attempt, however, proved to be unsuccessful. Reimplementing the code was very hard, as the functions lacked proper documentation and there were significant differences between the versions of the Tensorflow library. The lack of documentation made debugging a very challenging task.

In addition to the above challenges, another issue that we had to tackle was fixing the encoding of the labels. The method used in the repository for encoding the labels was not working properly, as it relied on libraries that were no longer maintained. This required us to find a solution that would be more compatible with the current libraries and technology.

4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the authors of the repository have a major task ahead of them in order to make the PRED component of the code functional and up-to-date with the latest libraries. This process will require a comprehensive re-working of the code to ensure it is runnable and able to produce validated results.

In addition to revising the code, the authors must also provide clear and concise documentation for the files contained within the repository. This documentation should include an explanation of the purpose of each file, as well as an overview of the code used to produce the results. This level of detail will be essential for ensuring the reproducibility of the results.

Despite the best efforts of our team to revise the code, update libraries, and remove unused parts, the PRED mechanism has proven to be a difficult task to reproduce. Despite this setback, the authors must continue to work towards making the code runnable and producing validated results. Only then will the results of the PRED mechanism be able to be confidently used and relied upon.

5 REFERENCES

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